

THE DIFFERENCES IN STUDENTS' WRITING PROCESS BASED ON PERSONALITY TRAITS

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Abstract: This research investigates the differences in the writing process between introverted and extroverted university students. The research used a qualitative method with a case study design. The subject of the research consisted of ten students, six of whom were introverted and four of whom were extroverted. The instruments used were a questionnaire, an interview, an observation, and a document analysis. The results of this research show significant differences at every stage in the writing process. Introverted students typically begin with in-depth and systematic planning, relying on ideas generated from internal thoughts and enriched by solitary activities, but often struggle with choosing a topic and tend to create a detailed outline. When drafting, they work systematically and carefully, taking their time and remaining quiet, although they sometimes struggle to combine ideas. In editing, they conduct in-depth and time-consuming independent revisions due to their perfectionist nature. In the finalization stage, they conduct thorough checks to ensure the final quality of the writing is independently verified. In contrast, extroverted students rely more on social interactions and trends as triggers for ideas, tend to write spontaneously without in-depth planning, which can pose challenges in the independence of ideas and the organization of writing. When drafting, they tend to be more spontaneous and rely on interactions to develop ideas, but may be less structured and struggle to deepen their ideas. In editing, although they write faster, they still require revisions and greatly benefit from feedback from others. In the finalization stage, they are more enthusiastic about sharing their work immediately and are open to criticism. Understanding these distinctions can inform the refinement of pedagogical strategies and enhance student preparedness.

Keywords: *writing process, introvert, extrovert, university student*

1. INTRODUCTION

Writing is a fundamental communication tool, enabling the articulation of ideas, knowledge, emotions, and perspectives through textual representation. Harmer (2004) suggests that writing is a tool for producing language and expressing ideas, emotions, and opinions. He also emphasizes the importance of genre conventions in the writing process and advocates for their inclusion in learning activities. For university students, it is not merely a means of conveying information but also a critical instrument for critical thinking and analysis, essential for both academic success and professional advancement (Graham & Perin, 2007).

Individual writing approaches are shaped by various factors, including personality, intelligence, learning style, and motivation (Hunayli, 2022; Rahardi et al., 2024). According to Erton, as cited in Hunayli (2022), student's personality significantly influences writing learning outcomes and the writing process itself. Personality, a core psychological construct, dictates how individuals interact with their environment and engage with tasks, including complex ones like writing. It plays a significant role in shaping an individual's writing process.

Personality theory often categorizes individuals as introverts or extroverts, each exhibiting distinct characteristics and preferences (H. J. Eysenck, 2017). Introverts, as described by Eysenck and Eysenck (1965), are naturally more reserved and inclined towards deep thought. This tendency directly impacts their writing approach; they

often dedicate substantial time to contemplation and reflection before putting pen to paper. Moreover, they often prefer independent thought and solitary work. Several studies suggest that introverts are more precise in their writing and tend to be better EFL writing learners (Boroujeni et al., 2015; Esmailpour & Babaei, 2025; Qanwal & Ghani, 2019; Ramadhan, 2019; Sirajuddin et al., 2023). In contrast, extroverts, also noted by Eysenck and Eysenck (1965), are characterized by their outgoing, energetic, and sociable nature. They tend to favor collaborative idea sharing and teamwork. These inherent traits similarly influence their writing approach; they prefer sharing ideas, collaboration, and spontaneous writing (Aqariza & Authar, 2020; Mirhosseini & Abousaeedi, 2023; Olalekan, 2024).

The relations between personality (introversion and extroversion) and writing ability or performance have been explored by several researchers (Boroujeni et al., 2015; Esmailpour & Babaei, 2025; Sahid et al., 2023; Sirajuddin et al., 2023; Zaswita & Ihsan, 2020). Thus, this study's novelty lies in its specific focus on the relation between personality and the writing process, especially the differences between introverted and extroverted students.

To examine the research problem, this research uses a basic theory of the writing process from Harmer (2004) who outlines the writing process as a four-stage progression: (1) planning; in this stage three crucial elements are emphasized which are defining the purpose (which dictates language and information), identifying the target audience (shaping tone and style), and structuring the content logically, (2) drafting stage entails producing the initial written version, requiring ample time for students to develop and organize their ideas effectively, (3) editing stage involves students reviewing their work, often exchanging feedback, to identify and revise unclear information or grammatical errors, and to refine vocabulary for enhanced variety and interest, and (4) final version is the polished text ready for submission, often significantly altered from the initial draft due to extensive editing, with unnecessary information removed to ensure conciseness and effectiveness.

This study also uses the stages of the writing process based on personality, a theory from Eysenck and Eysenck (1965), to analyze the differences between introverts and extroverts. He proposes that introverts and extroverts navigate the stages of essay composition differently. Introverts typically approach writing with a methodical and thorough process. Their (1) brainstorming often occurs in solitude, employing techniques like mind maps or simply taking notes as ideas emerge. Following this, (2) organizing is a crucial step where they meticulously structure their ideas, frequently creating detailed outlines to ensure a smooth flow in their writing. During (3) drafting, introverts tend to be precise and careful, often revising their work multiple times to ensure clarity and correctness. The (4) revising and editing stage is characterized by perfectionism; they meticulously reread their work to identify errors and enhance clarity. Finally, for the (5) final version, introverts prioritize thoroughness and quality, conducting a comprehensive check for errors to ensure the work is polished before submission. A deep reflection on the process and product is also common, serving as a means of learning and self-development.

In contrast, extroverts often engage with the writing process in a more interactive and dynamic manner. Their (1) brainstorming frequently involves discussions with others, as they enjoy bouncing ideas off friends or colleagues and receiving immediate feedback. When (2) organizing, extroverts may jot down notes or create mind maps, perhaps less detailed than an introvert's outline, but still focused on establishing a logical flow. During (3) drafting, extroverts tend to write quickly and with confidence, unafraid to put down ideas even if not yet perfected. While they may write

rapidly, (4) revising and editing remain important, and they often benefit significantly from external feedback to refine their work. For the (5) final version, extroverts demonstrate eagerness to share their writing, driven by the motivation of social interaction and external feedback, viewing discussions and reactions to their work as valuable opportunities for learning and future skill development.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a qualitative research methodology, specifically employing a case study approach to thoroughly investigate the intricacies of students' writing processes. Qualitative descriptive research inherently seeks to illuminate real-world phenomena by gathering rich, detailed information directly from individuals with firsthand experience. As an in-depth analytical strategy for identifiable cases with defined boundaries, or for comparing multiple cases, a case study proves particularly effective. Patnaik & Pandey (2019) underscore the value of case research for examining contemporary phenomena within their natural contexts, aligning with the objectives of this study.

This study was conducted at one of the universities in Surakarta, focusing on a cohort of second-semester English Education students. This class comprised a total of 38 students. Within this group, 16 students were identified as having an introverted personality, while 18 students exhibited extroverted traits. For the purpose of an in-depth investigation, 10 students were purposively selected: 6 with introverted personalities and 4 with extroverted personalities.

The researchers employed four distinct instruments for data collection. (1) A questionnaire was used to identify personality types. The researchers administered an adapted version of the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ) (Eysenck et al., 1985), a well-established instrument developed by Hans J. Eysenck. Its design and application followed criteria from similar previous research. Additionally, (2) observations were conducted, ranging from informal notes on body language and interactions to more formal structured assessments, providing valuable qualitative insights for the analysis (Sullivan-Bolyai & Bova, 2021). (3) A crucial data source was the documentation of writing assignments from English Education students in class 2D. Analyzing these documents allowed for an in-depth examination of the assignments, serving as a reference for writing assessment and helping to discern how student personalities might be reflected in their writing, particularly regarding differences in structure and creativity between extroverted and introverted students (Sullivan-Bolyai & Bova, 2021). Finally, (4) interviews were used to gather qualitative data, eliciting detailed descriptions from participants concerning specific research questions (Taherdoost, 2022).

3. RESULTS

As the aim of this study is to explore the differences in the writing process of introverted and extroverted students when composing an essay, the differences will be analyzed by dividing the writing process into four stages based on Harmer (2004) and Eysenck and Eysenck (1965): planning (brainstorming and organizing), drafting, revising and editing, and final version.

3.1. Planning

In this stage, the writing process follows five aspects: (1) first step, (2) outline, (3) determine the title and find references, (4) the importance of the planning stage in the writing process, and (5) difficulties in the planning step.

In the first step (1), introverted students tend to engage in deep reflection, carefully considering the main idea and supporting arguments before going further. Petric (2022) noted that the brainstorming process for an introvert involves a careful consideration of various options and thorough planning. S7 stated that *“Langkah pertama adalah menentukan tema atau judul atau ide,...”*. The same statement was also mentioned by S1, S3, S6, and S10. While extroverted students are more responsive to popular trends, making them appear more current in their choice of topics. Four students with extroverted personalities stated that they looked for topics, ideas, and references. They tended to observe hot issues happening currently.

“Memikirkan beberapa topik lalu membandingkan, apa saja yang saya bandingkan (hot issue, kemudahan mengumpulkan informasi, dan kesetaraan antara pemahaman diri saya dan topik” (S8).

“Yang pertama cari ide, jelas... google, atau tiktok, atau ig buat yang cari referensi ini enaknya dibuat kemana” (S5).

When doing outlining (2), introverts' tendency towards perfectionism and deep attention to detail causes them to spend more time outlining texts than extroverts, as was done S1, S3, S7, and S10.

“...jadi rencana itu terdiri dari menemukan ide pokok terlebih dahulu lalu memikirkan berapa paragraf yang akan dituliskan setelah itu menemukan thesis paragraf lalu akhirnya memikirkan isi untuk melengkapi paragraf-paragraf, mencari fakta-fakta untuk mendukung isi dari paragraf termasuk pendapat para ahli, dan mensortir lagi kata kata dalam paragraf untuk merapikan kalimat agar lebih runtut dan jelas” (S10).

In contrast, extroverted students are generally more spontaneous and impulsive in generating writing ideas. They tend to write down ideas that come to them without delay, and only then verify their truth through research or discussion with experts. Most of the students interviewed answered that they did not make outlines; they tended to write spontaneously when they got ideas and references, as mentioned by S5, *“...ga pernah buat outline atau rencana.... secara garis besar kan, caranya doang”*.

In the third aspect, which determines the title and finds references (3), the idea-seeking process for introverts often involves self-reflection, for example, S1 and S6, who chose themes related to their personality or the formulation of opinions rooted in personal views, which were further reinforced by credible sources, *“lebih ke nentuin topik secara pribadi kak, biar lebih fokus terus sudah tau gambaran seperti*

apa tulisan yang mau ditulis nanti” (S1). Five students with introverted personalities argued that they tended to think about themes or titles without discussing them with their friends or determining them personally. S3, S7, and S10 argued that they looked for references before writing an outline, *“betul, saya mencari referensi terlebih dahulu,..., rencana untuk tulisan bisa lebih matang dan lebih baik”* (S10). Conversely, trend-sensitive extroverts, while perhaps bringing up topics close to their hearts, still keep an eye on current developments. Extroverted students tend to understand hot issues in their environment, because they often interact with many people. They tended to involve others in the process of exploring their ideas through discussion, *“saya cenderung berpikir sendiri terlebih dahulu.... lalu kadang berdiskusi dengan teman untuk mendapat masukan”* (S9). In searching for reference, extroverted students did it before outlining to make the writing process easier, *“...mencari referensi terlebih dahulu sebelum membuat outline...”* (S9).

The next one is the importance of the planning stage in the writing process (4). Both introverted and extroverted students agreed with the opinion that this planning process is very important to help students in the writing process, be more organized, and more efficient. One of the introverted students explained below.

“Sangat penting kak, karena dengan rencana yang jelas, jadi tau mau menulis apa, alurnya bagaimana, dan poin pentingnya apa saja. Jadinya lebih efisien, dan tidak membuang-buang waktu untuk berpikir di tengah jalan, lalu hasil tulisannya juga lebih enak dibaca.” (S10)

The same opinion from extroverted students, such as S8 and S9, stated that making an outline in the planning process was important because it helped to know the direction of the writing and avoid writing block, *“tahap perencanaan sangat penting karena membantu mengatur ide, menentukan tujuan tulisan, dan membuat proses menulis lebih terarah”* (S9).

The last aspect is difficulties in the planning step (5). Two opinions emerged regarding the difficulties experienced in this planning step, which are combining ideas and a lack of references. When it comes to selecting ideas, introverted students tended to face difficulties due to the abundance of ideas they wanted to express, which were often triggered by various references from personal interests and strong imagination, as remarked by S7, *“kesulitannya di penggabungan ide ide dan penempatannya yang cocok dan baik secara aturan”*. Further S6 had difficulty in finding references, *“salah satunya adalah kekurangan sumber materi ataupun bahan untuk dibuat referensi”*. Extroverted students also had difficulty choosing ideas because they tended to rely on social interactions, discussions, or trends as their main sources of inspiration. They had difficulty organizing these ideas into coherent paragraphs and needed help writing them in clear sentences, as pointed out by S9 *“...Mungkin kesulitannya di mencari ide, nyari tema, nyari judul. Pas udah ketemu semua isinya gimana...”*.

3.2. Drafting

In the drafting stage, four aspects are examined, which are: (1) drafting steps, (2) how to write, (3) difficulty developing ideas, and (4) how to overcome difficulties.

The first aspect, which is drafting steps (1), shows that introverted and extroverted students are different. Introverted students often include a more methodical way of working and following a pre-made plan. They answered that they immediately wrote the first draft according to the writing plan they had made. This is

because they followed the plan that had been made previously, remarked S10, *“langsung menyusun draft langkah awal menurut rencana penulisan”*. Another student stated similar opinion below.

“Untuk penulisan draft aku langsung mengikuti outline yang udah ditentukan kak, penulisan pendahuluan itu penting si buat kita bisa mengenalkan topik dari tulisan yang akan kita tulis, selain itu dari pendahuluan juga kita bisa mengencangkan tulisan untuk outline selanjutnya.” (S1)

For some extroverted students, a plan is simply an outline of an idea, and they prefer to write down whatever comes to mind at the time, resulting in a “spontaneous” writing style in which they may start without elaborate details and focus more on expressing ideas, as indicated by S5 who immediately wrote a draft, *“paling ya... langsung aja, langsung aja”*. S4, S8, and S9 said that they would first collect sources used in the text, make a conclusion, and then start writing. It was mentioned by S9, *“kalo aku sih... ngumpulin apa aja yang mau dimasukin ke tulisan mbak, jadi kayak teratur gitu”*.

The next aspect is how to write (2). Students with introverted personalities expressed their way of writing sequentially according to their planning guide, and following the example text to avoid being confused in working on it. S6 mentioned, *“saya menulis secara urut, berurutan, sesuai dengan contoh materi atau buku”* and S10 also asserted it, *“berurutan dari awal hingga akhir, karena kalau lompat-lompat takutnya bingung”*. Two ways of writing were followed by extroverted students. Some might follow a predetermined plan, while others tended to move between sections according to sudden ideas that arose while writing. S5, S8, and S9 created drafts according to the planning in the form of previously made outlines to understand the objectives better and what would be written, as conveyed by S8, *“berurutan mbak sesuai sama yang udah di tulis sebelumnya, kalo ga gitu aku ngerasa kesulitan”*. Meanwhile, S4 preferred writing in a jumpy manner because they wrote according to the ideas that came up first, without a detailed outline, and spontaneously, as stated, *“lompat-lompat sih.... point pertamanya baru di jelasin tentang apa. Habis itu di jelasin keadaannya apa segala macem. Abis itu di paragraf berikutnya yang dipoin kedua....”*.

In difficulty developing ideas (3), introverted students often struggled to combine various ideas into a coherent piece of writing. They had difficulty combining sentences and choosing words to express their ideas.

“Banyak sih kak. Pertama memilih kata-kata yang tepat buat menjelaskan ide-ide secara jelas. Kedua, membuat kalimat pendukung yang bisa memperkuat gagasan utama. Terus kadang juga kehabisan ide ditengah menulis jadinya paragrafnya kerasa kurang lengkap” (S1).

“Iya saya kesulitan mendeskripsikan ide-ide yang ada dalam kepala saya” (S3).

Extroverted personalities have challenges in developing limited ideas into longer and more in-depth texts. They struggled in choosing matching words, connecting existing facts, running out of material, and developing small ideas into fairly long paragraphs. Three students explained it, *“iya, emang sulit banget buat ngembangin dari ide-ide kecil menjadi paragraf yang lumayan panjang itu lumayan susah”* (S4), *“...nerjemahin dari bahasa bahasa pondok ke bahasa inggris itu agak sulit. Sama kalo nanti kehabisan materi, yang ada di pondok itu udah semua tak*

ceritain....” (S5), and “kesulitan yang saya alami adalah mencocokkan hubungan antara fakta dan konjungsi yang saya buat antar kata” (S8).

The last aspect in the drafting stage is how to overcome difficulties (4). Introverted students tend to choose a quiet and individually reflective approach. When faced with a problem, they usually took time to think, looked for additional references, and reflected on their ideas deeply before writing them down. When feeling burnt out in thinking about the ideas written in their drafts, they would take a break. In addition, they tried to find other references, so they could get ideas and know how to write them.

“kalau kehabisan ide itu tandanya sedang burn out kak, jadi hal pertama yang dilakuin itu istirahat dulu biar pikiran lebih fresh..., terus aku biasanya juga membaca ulang tulisan yang udah kutulis ini..., terus buat lebih lanjut mengembangkan tulisan kita. mencari referensi dari berbagai sumber juga membantu banget kalo lagi kehabisan ide” (S1).

“Mencari referensi lebih banyak lagi, biasanya setelah membaca referensi lain, langsung terpikir kalimat apa yang akan ditulis selanjutnya” (S10).

Extroverted students tend to interact with others, for example, through discussions, to gain fresh perspectives on the topics they are going to write about. They enjoy the process of exchanging ideas with friends or acquaintances as a trigger for creativity and a generator of new ideas. S4 and S5 overcame difficulties in developing ideas by discussing with friends to apprehend the concept better, as stated by S5 “...nanti minta temen temen ku yang ada dipondok itu buat ngasih gambaran aja”. Meanwhile, S9 and S8 chose to read more references, “...udah mulai menulis sendiri lah ya, aku sih biasanya banyakin baca aja...” (S9).

3.3. Revising and Editing

In this process, the lecturer asked students to peer review their friends’ writing. Before the peer review was carried out by students, the lecturer first provided an example of how to make corrections. The lecturer took a sample of one student’s writing to be corrected per paragraph based on whether it was in accordance with the text guide, the content taken was clear and did not deviate, grammar, vocabulary, spelling, punctuation, and capitalization.

To produce quality writing, introverts usually take quite a long time because they are often perfectionists when it comes to editing. Students with introverted personalities conducted independent revisions by rereading the texts they had written and determining errors that needed to be corrected, such as spelling, punctuation, illogical words, and grammar. Noticed from the interview data, on average, students with introvert personalities had errors in punctuation.

“Sebelum saya melakukan revisi, saya biasanya membaca dulu. Membaca berulang kali untuk mendapatkan mana letak kesalahan saya. Kemudian baru saya merevisi dengan cara melihat terlebih dahulu mana yang salah dan yang benar.” (S6)

“Untuk revisi draft pertama itu menentukan isi atau paragraf terstruktur sesuai dengan gagasan utama. Juga menentukan kejelasan dan ketepatan kata dengan begitu kita bisa mengganti kata-kata yang sekiranya kurang logis atau membingungkan. Terus memperbaiki ejaan, tanda baca dan struktur kalimat agar lebih rapi dann mudahh dipahamin.” (S1)

The analyzed document from one of the introverted students, S6, shows that there are no significant errors or mistakes to be revised, highlighted in yellow.

Figure 1: Pre Editing Essay of S6

Although speed of writing is a characteristic of extroverts, they still have the responsibility to edit and revise their writing. Extroverted students carried out independent revisions in the section on changing words from informal to more formal, checking text structure, and grammatical errors. They needed to edit the correction of inappropriate words and sentences, and the use of incorrect reference words.

“Revisi katanya sering, soalnya kan ada yang kata-kata yang menurut kita enak di denger aja gitu seenggaknya. Revisiannya disitu sih, mengubah struktur katanya sama diubah ke bentuk yang lebih formal dan kurang tau juga mudah dipahami atau tidak” (S4).

“Revisi non-teknis Berfokus pada aspek formal atau tata tulis karya, pada pemilihan kata, penggunaan tanda baca, atau struktur yang digunakan” (S8).

The analyzed document of S4 below shows several yellow-highlighted errors or mistakes that need to be corrected.

Figure 2: Pre-Editing Essay of S4

Birthday Depression

Matsubayashi and Ueda's (2016) research in Japan, which says that birthdays are synonymous with celebrations **so** it can cause stress for people who do not have friends to celebrate. For most people, birthdays are special and fun days to **celebrate** with family or friends and celebrate other successes. However, not everyone feels happy on their birthday. They feel disappointed with their own expectations, past trauma, and fear of the future **can make** some people feel depressed. Instead of feeling special, they feel anxious, sad and have a tough birthday.

One of the **sadnesses** of birthdays is expectation and pressure. Birthdays are annual events like Christmas, New Year celebrations, and anniversaries. However, **that** can make one feel even more lonely and isolated as it is a time that is supposed to be about relationships and celebrations. There is often an expectation that you will be surrounded by people, have plans, and feel loved. When the reality doesn't match up to what is expected **such as** failed celebration plans, few people wishing you a happy birthday or anything else that makes feelings of loneliness arise. There may also be societal or self-pressure to make this day "perfect" such as planning an unforgettable party that has to be better than last year's, or to follow social media trends that are viewed with such fervor that it builds a fantasy of how the celebration should be by uploading "perfect" birthday photos. If the reality doesn't match it will feel disappointed.

Furthermore, underlying mental conditions or past trauma Usually birthday blues are temporary, with feelings of sadness or anxiety that peak around the birthday and fade shortly after. It is usually brought on by previous negative experiences with birthdays, relating to trauma in one's life, and bad experiences in an idyllic childhood. These emotions may include mild to moderate sadness, anxiety, or disappointment.

In addition, getting older is often a trigger for death anxiety for some people, especially the elderly, and this can affect how they feel on their birthday. Physical changes such as wrinkled skin, forgetfulness, and greying hair, as well as the awareness of approaching death, can be a source of anxiety and sadness. Excessive fear of death, known as thanatophobia, can exacerbate these feelings. Thanatophobia is often experienced by people with mental disorders such as panic attacks, anxiety disorders, or PTSD, and can make sufferers feel like their life is getting shorter. As a result, what should be a happy birthday can turn into a source of anxiety and sadness for them.

Birthdays, often thought of as special and happy occasions, are **belied** by the fact that not everyone experiences such happiness. Disappointment from unmet expectations, past trauma, underlying mental conditions, and fears of aging and death can turn what should be a happy day into a source of anxiety and sadness. The pressure to create the "perfect" celebration and follow social media trends only exacerbates feelings of isolation, emphasizing that the birthday experience is highly personalized and influenced by a variety of psychological and social factors.

Birthday depression is not actually a mental disorder, but rather triggered by psychological issues. **Anxiety is generally at the root of the birthday blues.** If you feel signs of anxiety that are starting to interfere with your thoughts and activities, try some of the following ways to overcome it: **Do** breathing techniques or meditation when feelings of sadness or anxiety arise on your birthday, **Reflect on the main reason these feelings arise on your birthday, Think about the positive side of birthdays, think about the benefits of getting older, for example you will be wiser or soon get a pension, avoid comparing your birthday celebration with others, Talk about your feelings with people you trust.** You can also celebrate your birthday in a way that is comfortable for you. Maybe you can celebrate it alone by doing **metime** and you can also celebrate just together with your partner.

3.4. Final Version

In preparing the final version, introverted students show high precision and neatness, paying attention to every detail. They tend to add sentences to clarify the flow and coherence of the paragraph, and immediately proceed to the editing stage after review.

"..., setiap kali ingin mengembangkan kalimat selalu kehabisan ide karena biasanya di otak hanya menyiapkan beberapa kalimat yang ingin ditulis dan setelah ditulis, dan ingin dikembangkan lagi selalu kebingungan untuk mencari kalimat yang tepat dan nyambung, dan biasanya kalau dikeadaan seperti itu harus mencari referensi referensi lagi yang mendukung paragraf, membuat waktu pembuatan penulisan menjadi lebih lama dari yang direncanakan" (S10).

This interview data is also confirmed by the final pieces of writing from the introverted students, one of whom was S6. The sample from S6 tended to extend and clarify sentences. The writing demonstrated attention to punctuation, grammar, and varied vocabulary choices. It was shown that there were no punctuation errors in the writing. However, there were a few vocabulary items that needed to be removed or replaced with more formal synonyms.

'While some people may disagree with modern teaching because it requires a smart device, a stable internet connection, and basic digital literacy—challenges that can be difficult for some—its benefits far outweigh

these drawbacks.' The word 'challenges' already implies difficulty, so saying 'can be difficult' is somewhat repetitive. Therefore, it can be omitted and simply written as 'challenges for some people'.

'Students benefit from flexible schedules, which make learning more relaxed,...' 'Make learning more relaxed' may sound a bit informal. You can replace the word 'relaxed' with 'comfortable'.

The final version of the essay written by S6 shows significant changes and corrections, although there are still errors or mistakes that need to be corrected. It is noticeable that the essay appears longer, suggesting that additional information and references were added. Despite S6 having added more information, not many errors or mistakes were found.

Figure 3: Final Version of Essay of S6

Modern Teaching

[Redacted]

"The best teachers are those who show you where to look but don't tell you what to see." —
Alexandra K. Trenfor

In today's **modern** society, many things have become more convenient. We can order food with the press of a button, travel long distances by booking an online driver, and, most importantly, learn a vast range of subjects through modern teaching methods. While some people may disagree with modern teaching because it requires a smart device, a stable internet connection, and basic digital literacy—challenges **for some people**—its benefits far outweigh these drawbacks. Modern teaching is far more engaging, flexible, and effective than traditional teaching.

Firstly, modern teaching incorporates more games, quizzes, and interactive activities **compared to** (than) traditional methods. Why? **Because** students today are more engaged with their smartphones and the internet than with reading books. This phenomenon occurs due to their attachment to technology. With modern teaching methods, students can watch educational videos from platforms like Ruang Guru, which not only explains academic concepts but also integrate games to keep students entertained. Additionally, students can use educational apps such as Duolingo and Quizizz to enhance their learning experience. Modern teaching motivates students to be more courageous and determined in their studies while allowing teachers to monitor their progress effectively.

Secondly, "Flexibility is the key to stability." Modern teaching allows teachers to educate students anytime and anywhere. Applications such as Google Classroom, YouTube, Zoom, and Google Meet enable teachers to deliver lessons beyond the confines of a physical classroom. Students benefit from flexible schedules, which make learning more relaxed (**comfortable**), while teachers **benefit from more efficient lessons** (**komponen negatif bisa di ganti bisa di ganti**) can deliver lessons more efficiently, regardless of time or location.

Lastly, modern teaching surpasses traditional methods in terms of accessibility. Unlike traditional teaching, which relies solely on local textbooks, modern teaching provides access to a vast collection of books and resources available on the internet. This helps educators stay updated with the latest curricula and ensures that students receive relevant and comprehensive knowledge.

Though modern teaching offers many advantages, some may argue that it could entirely replace traditional teaching. However, modern teaching is deeply rooted in traditional methods, incorporating books, classrooms, and face-to-face learning. Therefore, it is unlikely that modern teaching will completely replace traditional teaching; rather, it enhances and complements it.

Given the numerous benefits, we, as the next generation of teachers, must embrace modern teaching methods. By understanding and applying these techniques, we can pass on our knowledge to future students while ensuring our teaching methods remain up-to-date and enjoyable. In a world filled with endless opportunities for learning, we must not confine

ourselves to outdated practices. Instead, we should harness modern technology to gain more knowledge and become successful individuals in the future.

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On the other hand, extroverted students produce a final version of their writing with adequate neatness, correcting the corrected parts reviewed by others without checking for other potential errors. They consider their final writing to be logical, clear, and relevant to the intended audience.

"Kitanya tau apa yang ingin kita tulis dan siapa yang kita tuju. Dan agar yang membacanya juga lebih tau juga apa yang dimaksud dari yang tulis oleh penulis tersebut. Kan ada yang namanya writer purpose tujuan dari sang penulis itu apa, apakah untuk entertaint ataukah untuk menginformasikan atau bahkan hanya sekedar menghibur." (S4)

The final version of the essay from one of the extroverted students, S4, also shows some changes. Similar to introverted students, it appears longer with additional information and references. However, it is noticeable that there are more highlighted errors or mistakes. It supports the tendency that after writing, extroverts usually do not recheck for other potential errors or mistakes.

Figure 4: Final Version of Essay of S4

<p style="text-align: center;">Birthday Depression</p> <p>Matsubayashi and Ueda's (2016) research in Japan, which says that birthdays are synonymous with celebrations so it can cause stress for people who do not have friends to celebrate. For most people, birthdays are special and fun days to celebrate with family or friends and celebrate other successes. However, not everyone feels happy on their birthday. They feel disappointed with their own expectations, past trauma, and fear of the future can make some people feel depressed. Instead of feeling special, they feel anxious, sad and have a tough birthday.</p> <p>One of the sadnesses of birthdays is expectation and pressure. Birthdays are annual events like Christmas, New Year celebrations, and anniversaries. However, that can make one feel even more lonely and isolated as it is a time that is supposed to be about relationships and celebrations. There is often an expectation that you will be surrounded by people, have plans, and feel loved. When the reality doesn't match up to what is expected such as failed celebration plans, few people wishing you a happy birthday or anything else that makes feelings of loneliness arise. There may also be societal or self-pressure to make this day "perfect" such as planning an unforgettable party that has to be better than last year's, or to follow social media trends that are viewed with such fervor that it builds a fantasy of how the celebration should be by uploading "perfect" birthday photos. If the reality doesn't match it will feel disappointed.</p> <p>Furthermore, underlying mental conditions or past trauma Usually birthday blues are temporary, with feelings of sadness or anxiety that peak around the birthday and fade shortly after. It is usually brought on by previous negative experiences with birthdays, relating to trauma in one's life, and bad experiences in an idyllic childhood. These emotions may include mild to moderate sadness, anxiety, or disappointment.</p> <p>In addition, getting older is often a trigger for death anxiety for some people, especially the elderly, and this can affect how they feel on their birthday. Physical changes such as wrinkled skin, forgetfulness, and greying hair, as well as the awareness of approaching death, can be a source of anxiety and sadness. Excessive fear of death, known as thanatophobia, can</p>	<p>exacerbate these feelings. Thanatophobia is often experienced by people with mental disorders such as panic attacks, anxiety disorders, or PTSD, and can make sufferers feel like their life is getting shorter. As a result, what should be a happy birthday can turn into a source of anxiety and sadness for them.</p> <p>It is true that birthdays can cause anxiety and depression in some people, however, birthdays also have a positive side. Birthdays can be a way to get together with family and other loved ones at one time, have a meaningful celebration party, get presents. Although birthdays have a happy side, research shows that birthdays can increase feelings of loneliness and isolation. Fear of aging and death can turn what should be a happy day into a source of anxiety and sadness. Expectations often don't match up to reality when birthdays arrive. In addition, constant exposure to birthday content on social media can trigger pressure to create the "perfect" celebration, leading to social media comparisons that ultimately damage mental health.</p> <p>Birthdays, which should be a happy occasion, can trigger stress and sadness for some people. This is due to a variety of factors, such as unrealistic expectations, social pressure, past trauma and fear of aging. The "birthday blues" is not a mental disorder, but a psychological response to these factors. Remedies include breathing techniques, avoiding comparisons, and celebrating in a comfortable way.</p> <p>Reference:</p> <p>Lam, Nicone., Ageing happens. Pay attention though, to prolonged 'birthday depression'. Acces from: https://www.channelnewsasia.com/today/mental-health-matters/birthday-blues-depression-milestone-anxiety-sad-4670746.</p> <p>LM Psikologi UGM. (2020, 25 Desember). Ulang Tahun, Tapi Kok Malah Sedih?!. Acces from: https://lm.psikologi.ugm.ac.id/2020/12/fun-fact-birthday-blues/.</p>
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4. CONCLUSION

The process of writing for individuals is varied depending on their personality. Introverts tend to reflect deeply and develop detailed outlines independently, while extroverts are more responsive to trends and seek ideas through social interaction. Introverts tend to write systematically and follow a plan when drafting, whereas extroverts may write more spontaneously and jump between sections. Introverts prefer careful, independent revision when editing, while extroverts often benefit from feedback from others. These differences reflect different energy orientations, with introverts focusing on the internal world and extroverts on the external world. However, both personality types have their own strengths and challenges at each stage of writing. Understanding these differences can help individuals recognize their preferences and develop more effective writing strategies.

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